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JAPANESE PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE INSTRUCTION

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ABSTRACT

In today's highly interconnected world, having strong English communication skills is essential. This article is devoted to studying pedagogical strategies employed in Japan to enhance English language instruction. By examining traditional and current methods, this study highlights the effectiveness of these strategies and their impact on student engagement, language proficiency, and cultural understanding.

Keywords: *Japanese pedagogical strategies, language learning, EFL environment, communication skills.*

INTRODUCTION

Traditionally, English language education in Japan has centered around rote memorization and a focus on grammar. However, with the advent of globalization and the recognition of English's importance in international communication, there has been a shift toward more interactive and student-centered approaches. Today, technology's role in language instruction has significantly altered the educational landscape. Digital tools such as language learning apps, online resources, and multimedia presentations are increasingly incorporated into English lessons. These tools cater to various learning styles and provide students with opportunities for self-directed learning. Moreover, online platforms facilitate connections between students and native speakers, promoting authentic language use. Despite the innovative strategies employed in Japanese English language instruction, several challenges remain. These include:

- **Exam-oriented Education.** The pressure to perform well on standardized tests often leads to a focus on grammar and vocabulary at the expense of communicative competence.

- **Teacher Training.** Many English teachers may lack adequate training in modern pedagogical methods, which can decrease the effective implementation of new strategies.
- **Cultural Attitudes.** The fear of making mistakes can discourage students from participating actively in speaking activities.

All points mentioned above will be discussed in this scientific article, analyzing each circular aspect of the way of teaching foreign languages in Japan.

METHODS

During this scientific research, qualitative and secondary data analysis methods were utilized, and previous researches were analysed to indicate outcomes of language teaching methods in Japan. The Japanese educational system with regard to ELT 3.1 An overview of English schooling. The Japanese education system is divided into three levels: primary, lower and upper secondary, and postsecondary education, which are organized in a 6-3-3-4 structure. Regarding the stages in the development of ELT in Japan, Stewart describes that in 2003, as a response to globalization, the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science, and Technology (from this point on MEXT) issued a policy directive requiring state secondary school English teachers to shift away from translation-based English teaching and towards activities that emphasize oral communication. In 2008, the Central Council for Education (CCE) officially proposed this common standard to align government educational policies with the demands of globalization. Therefore, it was determined that revisions were necessary to the current National Centre Test for University Admissions in order to achieve this goal. The concept of a “common standard for learning outcomes” seeks to create a more accurate teaching experience across university campuses and serves as a basis for evaluating whether educational goals have been achieved. This approach, also known as quality assurance, provides an educational policy that shifts away from diversity and flexibility and towards an embrace of worldwide standards. As a result, it is clear that MEXT employs quality assurance to standardize activities that promote oral communication in secondary school English sessions. National Standards for School Curriculum are typically modified every ten years. These curricular reforms are designed and implemented with the goal of raising standards and thereby improving educational quality. The frequency and extent with which reforms occur are heavily influenced by the sociocultural setting. As discussed above, it is widely acknowledged that what is learnt in school is directly tied to tests completed at the ages of 16 and 17. Because English was the most important language for passing entrance exams, pupils were taught to read and write in it, with grammatical analyses and translations to and from

Japanese serving as major approaches. Students completed a lot of drills and repetitions in class, and they were hardly given any chances to participate in group problem-solving, debate, or express their viewpoints. In big classrooms, teacher-centered and lecture-style instruction proved to be highly effective in achieving these entrance examination-oriented aims. In 2002, the introduction of “Yutori” or “low pressure/no cramming” education aimed to counter the traditional reliance on teacher-centered rote learning. Yutori-style education resulted in pupils spending 15% less time in the classroom studying fundamental subjects including mathematics, physics, and Japanese. Furthermore, pupils were no longer required to study in school on Saturday mornings, resulting in a simultaneous 30% reduction in the quantity of classroom work. Though Yutori education was quickly abandoned, the notion that “school should focus on helping students gain academic knowledge” became more firmly established in the public realm. Due to recent changes in English testing at the secondary level, which emphasize university entrance exams and frequent assessments of vocabulary and grammar, first-year students at Tokyo University of Science (TUS) often have a strong awareness of English structure but lack proficiency in oral communication. To acquire a better grasp of the context in which ELT occurs, one must first examine the elements that contributed to the current system. The following part is on teacher tactics for dealing with ELT reform, specifically how academic success is measured via active learning.

RESULTS

A state of flux in ELT.

Up to this point, more widespread implementation of a student-centered active learning strategy has had little effectiveness. Although large-scale improvements in the adoption of active learning at universities remain challenging, likely due to the numerous small-scale studies lacking statistical significance, policy reforms have nonetheless spurred English language teaching (ELT) curriculum changes at various levels. As a result, there is now a greater emphasis on communication skills rather than grammar. Thus, curriculum reform along with government policy directives pave the way for a new kind of English instruction. Whereas formerly, passive students in teacher-centered lectures would absorb what the teacher provided, there is now an increasing percentage of active students speaking with one another. University classroom tests and assessments are reflections of societal ideals. A shift towards more active learning in tertiary-level English Language Teaching (ELT) courses in Japan reflects a societal change in the skills that graduates are expected to possess when entering the workforce. As is, a graduating student should not only be able to think critically, actively interrupt, and make suggestions, but also to ask either the teacher or classmates for clarification of intended meaning, allowing ideas to be exchanged and

new ideas, concepts, and hypotheses to be developed. As a result, it is clear that some method of evaluating these skills through the evaluation of academic performance is required. In the context of TUS, this method has changed from a single formal final examination at the end of a course of study to a range of assessments that evaluate academic performance throughout the course.

DISCUSSION

With the development of instructional activities that allow for more spoken communication during lessons, ELT reform in Japan is progressing. Though difficult to carry out, these lesson plans, also known as communicative language teaching (CLT), are essential to teaching in the setting of English as a foreign language (EFL). Reporting on any innovations in teaching practice brought about by policy reform, as well as the dynamic interaction between institutional setting and the mindset of educators, is crucial. However, there is still the matter of how college instructors evaluate students' academic performance in their classes. The degree to which CLT activities are considered appropriate for the current educational culture is one barrier to their acceptance in EFL environments. There is a conflict in explanation between "communicative competence" and "cultural continuity", as defined by Holliday. At that time, Ikeda observes that students typically show a "lack of wordiness" in their first language that is appropriate for their culture when participating in CLT activities in Japan. It would make sense for teachers to evaluate academic success by concentrating on students' proficiency in English when there is a seemingly static low level of oral communication competence and a teaching strategy that demands a particular level to be met. Cultural understanding is also vital for effective language learning. Japanese educators often incorporate cultural elements into their English lessons, exposing students to different aspects of English-speaking cultures through literature, films, and music. Having said that, exchange programs and study abroad opportunities allow students to experience immersive environments where they can practice their language skills in real-world contexts.

CONCLUSION

Japanese pedagogical strategies for enhancing English language instruction reflect a commitment to improving communication skills among students. By embracing communicative approaches, task-based learning, technology integration, and cultural immersion, educators are fostering a more dynamic and engaging learning environment. However, addressing the challenges inherent in the education system is essential for maximizing the potential of these strategies. Continued investment in teacher training and curriculum development will be crucial for sustaining progress in English language education in Japan.

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